

Scienxt Journal of Emerging Technologies in Electronics Engineering

Volume-2 // Issue-3 // Sept-Dec // Year-2024 // pp. 21-33

Adaptive MPPT control for hybrid wind-solar power systems

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Abstract:

Nowadays meeting out the daily power demand is to be the important criteria in the case of power generation system. Because daily power needs is keen on increasing daily basis. As the customers are requiring more demand over the electricity demand, it is the utmost important thing to concentrate more on it. In this paper it is to go for utilizing the Renewable Energy Sources (RES) for meeting out such power demand estimation. For that we are moving ahead of utilizing the Hybrid Wind-Solar Power Systems (HWSPS) in our paper. Not only that but also going to use the Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) method to harness maximum possible electrical power from those RES optimally. Here we are with the suitable Adaptive MPPT method to address that challenges in response to the real time scenario in the case of HWSPS. In this technique we are going to adopt some techniques like particle swarm optimization and fuzzy logic control for the efficient harness of the utilization of the RES. These methods used only for the efficient optimization of the power output in the HWSPS. The results showed that the power output from the HWSPS is improved efficiently when compare with the performances of the other or conventional MPPT techniques with our adaptive MPPT techniques.

Keywords:

MPPT for PV-Wind, PV system, Wind energy Conversion System (WECS), Maximum power extraction with MPPT.

1. Introduction:

The important consideration that comes to our mind is that the optimal deployment of the available cleaner and greener RES is the prerequisite thing to implement now. In addition to that the total world is approaching towards optimizing the RES due to which it is available in nature at free of cost. Even though we have so many RES available in nature, wind and solar are considerably available in better and more abundant form. That is why our research is moving ahead of ahead of HWSPS deployment. As we have a HWSPS deployment, it is an important aspect to consider its optimal design over the implementation of such RES in a combined form. Here we have two types of RES that are solar and wind energy.

We cannot sure that these RES will be available all throughout the day. Because it has intermittent characteristics feature by its nature. So to maximize the efficiency of this hybrid system is pretty challengeable because of its intermittent in nature. As we know that the sun light energy can be harnessed there for only 4.5 Hours per day whereas windy nature keeps on changing every time. That is why we are going ahead of using adaptive MPPT technique over here for addressing such challenges to harness more energy output form HWSPS optimally in order to meet out the power demand. This is the important function that MPPT will identify the maximum point at which it can generate more and the possible output from either of the RES on an average basis throughout the day.

Actually the primary requirement of both wind and solar energy output is actually different in nature. The solar plant requires solar panels also called as Photo Voltaic (PV) panels whereas the wind power plant has wind turbine .Furthermore its operating condition and the environmental aspects are totally different in nature. That is why it is necessary to go ahead of a certain technique to harness optimal energy output from both of the power plants.

Actually the conventional methods of MPPT such as Incremental conductance method (IC) and Perturb and Observe (PO) are experimentally being focused for the single power system source only. That is the point to be addressed those times when we don't have such adaptive MPPT technique which uses some metaheuristic approach which includes particle optimization technique as well as Genetic Algorithm (GA) approach. We just make use of the Fuzzy Logic Controller (FLC) to address the uncertainties and non-linearity occurring in nature of the energy output produced from the wind and solar.

Our research in this paper going to be focused on maximizing the energy from both of the RES. Comparing to the conventional MPPT method, the metaheuristic approach based MPPT provided impactful change in the harness tracing the all available energy from HWSPS. This method also making the possibility of using the HWSPS in an optimal form of harnessing the power output from both the wind and solar RESs.

2. Overview of hybrid wind-solar power systems:

Here the solar and wind power are going to be combined and to be connected back to the grid power supply. The HWSPS will be the effective one as we already discussed in the introduction section of this paper. The reason why we optimize such two available RESs is that the way it generates power supply is reliable and highly efficient in nature. Not only that but also it is needed to be installed in a same place so as to be connected to the same grid to get the efficient output. So that we can overcome and minimize the losses in the transmission of that generated power supply form HWSPS.

Figure. 1

The block diagram above has depicted the overall layout of the HWSPS. The PV array and the wind power plant both are connected in a same plant as a hybrid form. The power generated from the solar panel is normally Direct Current (DC) current. So that it needs to be converted back to Alternating Current (AC) by using suitable power electronics converter. At the same time the power generated from the wind power plant is actually fluctuating in nature. So that we need to convert it back to DC form of current. That is done by the respective power converters and feeding the AC current to the grid power station. This hybrid form of power generation from both

the wind and solar RESs is also called out to be multi sources power system. In addition to that there are some sophisticated specialized power converters are there for adjusting the voltage and frequency parameters to be fed back to the grid power supply station. Injecting the generated power supply directly to the grid is not possible due to the irregularities over the electrical parameters. The synchronization is highly recommended for the smooth injection generated power onto the grid units.

2.1. The objective of the HWSPS:

The concept behind this hybrid option is that if one power plant produces less power output which can be substantially balanced by the power generated by the other RESs based power plant optimally. This HWSPS will be delivering the power constantly and continually to the grid throughout the day and night without any compromise for the power shortage and outage. There are so many advantages used for the hybridization of the RESs.

2.1.1. Energy output reliability:

As the power produced from both the power plants facing the intermittency nature, it necessitates the hybridization need of the HWSPS. Due to the combination of the both power sources of wind and solar energy, the total system reduces the time of no power generation which leads to the continuity of the power to be supplied to the grid.

2.1.2. Optimized energy output:

Here we are using adaptive MPPT controller which can be well suitable for the hybrid option based power generation due to its optimization and harnessing the peak form of energy output. Traditional MPPT controller will not be the better option for the multi-source power system optimization but well suited for the single source energy optimization. Also this algorithm is capable to produce the dynamic adjustments over the real time scenario of power production and utilization in multi-source power supply synchronization.

2.1.3. Stability in grid integration:

As we already talked about the necessary electrical parameters need to be adjusted before injecting onto the grid the interconnection of all the SS (Sub-Station). The point to be considered here is that whenever there is a change in the solar irradiance or wind speed fluctuation occurs,

the adaptive MPPT will try to optimize the power generated output in order to help the total power system stability as well as helping to reduce the largest fluctuations in the power supply which affects the grid frequency.

3. Adaptive MPPT control strategy:

Figure. 2

In an adaptive control strategy the efficient way is to take control over the parameters of voltage and frequency that are to be injected onto the existing live power supply system. From the generated power supply we are about to check the parameters before moving ahead of synchronization. The adaptive MPPT will harness the maximum possible power output efficiently from the HWSPPS in order to overcome the intermittent power supply optimization. Reactive power compensation is an important control strategy in the case of optimization of the power output from the hybrid power system. That is why this system is making a control strategy over the minimization of the power losses in term of reactive power in our approach. This controller will consider the grid reactive power with that of the reactive powers retrieved from the power converters used in the HWSPPS and provide it as a quadrature current.

3.1. Solar output power control loop (MPPT):

There is a comparative analysis between the reference powers outputs from the PV panel with the output power from the boost converter used in the MPPT controller for the PV array power output.

Figure. 3

4. MPPT basic requirement for HWSPS:

Power generation system is facing constraints mainly due to the periodical and routine changes over the atmospheric condition. Especially its effect is more on the hybrid system of both wind and PV only. Then it is the prerequisite thing for a HWSPS to be adopted with efficient power extraction technique like an adaptive one for the efficient optimization.

4.1. MPPT performance in wind power plant:

There are two approaches actually followed in Wind Energy Conversion System (WECS) namely direct and indirect control approach. In an indirect power control technique the various factors are there to be modified and controlled such as optimal torque and Tip Speed Ratio (TSR). These methods will help the MPPT controller to optimize its turbine speed regulation in the WECS. The optimal TSR is to be maintained to harness the maximum power output for a MPPT controller in an adaptive manner. This method is requiring a certain parameters like air density, turbine mechanical strength and so on to harness the maximum and possible energy from the wind energy. The expression is given for an optimum mechanical torque of the WECS as follows.

$$T_{mech}^{optimum} = \frac{1}{2} \rho \pi R^2 \frac{C_p^{max}}{\lambda_{optimum}^{3.1}} \omega_m^2 = k_{optimum} W_m^2$$

The diagram below shows the various speed level of the wind turbine as per the wind speed to reach the optimum harness for a MPPT controller in WECS.

Figure. 4

4.2. MPPT approach in Solar:

It is necessary that to implement MPPT controller over the solar panel in order to enhance the maximum power output irrespective of the weather and load conditions. The MPPT implementation for a solar array is not as easy as that of WECS. Here in this approach, it needs to work across the feasible region of current and voltage parameters. The basic layout diagram of MPPT implementation on solar power output is given below.

Figure. 5

It is to act based upon the solar irradiance output from the PV panel output power. There are so many tracking methods are followed actually for solar based MPPT control implementation. All the power tracking methods will make use of sensors to obtain the voltage and current parameters. The sensors will give the optimal parameters report on which MPPT will harness its optimal power output.

4.3. Fuzzy solar based MPPT:

Actually the traditional MPPT techniques will be struggled with the non-linearity issues over the implementation but the adaptive techniques like the Fuzzy Logic Control (FLC) solar MPPT implementation will be able to handle some uncertainty situations as well as changing weather patterns to optimize the best and the possible power output. In this approach an inverter is operated with regard to the firing angles which is sent by the FLC based MPPT controller to adhere to the grid regulations. The prime point is that fuzzy based MPPT can be integrated onto the soft computing techniques. Initially there is no measurement from solar irradiance but the fuzzy system will drive system to reach the maximum possible power output.

The error formula is given as follows.

$$E(t) = \frac{\Delta P(t)}{\Delta V(t)} = \frac{P(t) - P(t-1)}{V(t) - V(t-1)}$$

Figure. 6

Anyway the FLC will use limited system of inputs at the beginning but later on it is to be optimized with multiple inputs for the maximum possible optimization of power output. Fuzzification, Fuzzy inference system and de-fuzzification are the three basic steps which are involved in fuzzy implementation for harnessing maximum possible energy output. Fuzzification process converts real data input to fuzzy values with the help of membership functions. Applying fuzzy inference system the fuzzy output region is marked and finally the fuzzy values are to be changed back to crisp values using defuzzification process.

4.4. Fuzzy wind based MPPT:

When we go for a grid connected WECS, this climatic condition will go for an abrupt changes in the magnitude and the frequency of the generated power output. That is why we are moving ahead of FLC based MPPT technique to address and overcome such issues. Further this implementation is to be checked under various magnitudes of velocity of the air for the smoother

and optimal power generation. There are some fuzzy controllers to control the flux of the motor and the speed of the rotor of that concerned motor.

Normally variable speed WECS will go out of the control because of its high wind speed which can be governed and controlled under FCL wind MPPT approach. Finally the WECS provided the better performance compare with the traditional MPPT control technique.

Figure. 7

5. Simulation and results:

The figure below shows the shading effect of the solar irradiance output using adaptive MPPT implementation. It is purely based on the sun light availability for the power generation.

Figure. 8

The below output shows the power generation from the PV array which is used to give constant power output during the implementation.

Figure. 9

This is the wind speed measurements in the particular place which is indicated in the diagram below. The graph is plotted based on wind speed with respect to time.

Figure. 10

The below power output clearly indicates that the consistent and smoothness has been clearly found in the power generation from the WECS.

Figure. 11

The created hybrid system with a single MPPT controller will provide an average DC link power of 587 W from 0 to 0.3 sec, 721 W from 0.3 to 0.6 sec, and 858.8 W from 0.6 to 0.9 sec which

can be clearly indicated in the below combined HWSPS power output which is successfully injected into the grid.

Figure. 12

6. Conclusion:

The electric load has been certainly increased in the past ten years. The meritorious substitute for reducing the burden on the main power systems is a solar power plant. In this paper, the FLC based MPPT and Adaptive-based MPPT implementation has been employed for load controls are investigated. In order to maintain output power, a smart transformer is also installed prior to load distribution. The Adaptive-based MPPT controller with converter features low fluctuations and fast tracking. Wind speed data and changes in solar irradiation are taken into consideration when evaluating the suggested MPPT performance in grid-connected power plants of HWSPS. By integrating Adaptive MPPT approach which was respond to the fluctuating nature of solar irradiance and windy conditions of HWSPS, it harnessed maximum power output from both the wind and solar power plants. To conclude, adaptive MPPT control is a vital and the useful technology that can help hybrid wind-solar power systems to attain their full potential and open the door for more efficient renewable energy sources. Further developments in adaptive MPPT techniques are probably going to improve these hybrid systems' performance even high as technology moves ahead.

7. References:

- (1) J. Prasanth Ram, N. Rajasekar, and Masafumi Miyatake, Design and overview of maximum power point tracking techniques in wind and solar photovoltaic systems: A review,

- Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, Volume 73, 2017, Pages 1138–1159, ISSN 1364-0321, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.02.009>.
- (2) Kumar, K., Lakshmi Devi, V., Dhanamjayulu, C., *et al.* Evaluation and deployment of a unified MPPT controller for hybrid Luo converters in combined PV and wind energy systems. *Sci Rep* 14, 3248 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-53605-z>
 - (3) Qusay Hassan, Sameer Algburi, Aws Zuhair Sameen, Hayder M. Salman, Marek Jaszczur, A review of hybrid renewable energy systems: solar and wind-powered solutions: challenges, opportunities, and policy implications, *Results in Engineering*, Volume 20, 2023, 101621, ISSN 2590-1230, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2023.101621>.
 - (4) G.badamosi, Saheed Lekan; Nwulu, Nnamdi I. (2020). Optimal Power Dispatch and Reliability Analysis of Hybrid CHP-PV-Wind Systems in Farming Applications, *Sustainability*, 12(19), 8199–. doi:10.3390/su12198199
 - (5) A.M. Hemeida, M.H. El-Ahmar, A.M. El-Sayed, Hany M. Hasanien, Salem Alkhalaf, M.F.C. Esmail, T. Senjyu, Optimum design of hybrid wind/PV energy system for remote areas, *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, Volume 11, Issue 1, 2020, Pages 11–23, ISSN 2090-4479, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asej.2019.08.005>.
 - (6) Sanjari, M. J., Gooi, H. B., and Nair, N-K.C. Power generation forecast of a hybrid PV-wind system. *IEEE Trans. Sustain. Energy* 11(2), 703–712. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSTE.2019.2903900> (2019).
 - (7) Das, S., & Akella, A. K. Power flow control of PV-wind-battery hybrid renewable energy systems for stand-alone applications. *Int. J. Renew. Energy Res.* 8(1), 36–43 (2018).
 - (8) Kumar, K., Ramesh Babu, N. & Prabhu, K. R. Design and analysis of RBFN-based single MPPT controller for hybrid solar and wind energy system. *IEEE Access* 5, 15308-15317 (2017). [DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2017.273355]